

Comparison of the Performance and Energy Efficiency Evaluation of 5G User-Plane Functions

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Abstract—While 5G has arrived with ambitious promises regarding the disruptive performance of the new applications it enables, its power consumption is raising several concerns especially for the user-plane, as such applications generate huge amounts of data. In order to better understand the issue, this paper compares two different type of User-Plane Functions (UPF), namely the Vector Packet Processing (VPP) and the Extended Berkeley Packet Filter - eXpress Data Path (eBPF-XDP). Results show better performances of the latter in certain conditions.

Keywords—5G, UPF, energy efficiency

I. INTRODUCTION

The fifth generation (5G) technology is the present and the future of the worldwide telecommunication systems. It fulfill stringent requirements such as Low Latency, Ultra-reliability, Massive Machine Type Communications and Enhanced Mobile Broadband not only focused on connecting people but also oriented to industries and the Internet of Things (IoT)

With respect to the previous technologies, 5G massively relies on Network Function Virtualization (NFV), Cloud Computing and Edge Computing that allow the deployment of the system near the final user, consequently having less latency and more reliability.

Those advantages have, unfortunately, a price in terms of energy requirement, in fact several studies indicate that the intrinsic distributed and pervasive nature of 5G and edge computing are going to cause a noticeable usage and deployment increase of computing resources, increasing the associated infra-structure OpEx and CapEx, and, consequently, their carbon footprint and energy requirements [1]-[4].

For these reasons, the objective of this paper is to compare two different type of User-Plane Functions (UPF), that represents the Data Plane of the 5G core system, in order to understand the consumption of power, focusing in particular, on different scenarios (different number of users generating variable traffic). The two kind of UPFs tested are the Vector Packet Processing (VPP) and the Extended Berkeley Packet Filter - eXpress Data Path (eBPF-XDP). Results show better performances of the latter in certain conditions.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows. Section II covers some basic principles behind the concept of green networking, while Section III describes the system setup used for the tests. Results of the performance evaluation can be found in Section IV and conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. GREEN NETWORKING

Nowadays, reducing CO₂ emissions is a key topic in all sectors of the world and so is the ICT sector, which consumes the 4.7% of the world's electricity, releasing about 1.7% of total greenhouse gas emissions [5]. Although cloud and edge computing bring huge benefits in 5G, the number of devices requiring services to the network is growing, so energy consumption has become an issue along with the associated carbon footprint. They also rely on powerful devices that require both power and air conditioning to keep them at the right temperature [6].

Until now, networks were deployed to sustain the peak hour traffic, therefore thinking only to the worst possible scenario, giving extra capacity to handle unexpected events. This way of designing networks is opposite to the principles of sustainability and green networking, since it provision redundant resources that are, most of the time, wasted (throwing bandwidth to the problem). The overall energy consumption is therefore increased because, in order to avoid fault in the infrastructure, devices are added with the only purpose of taking the duty of the broken/failed device.

In recent years, many efforts have been made to reduce unnecessary energy and resources use, which has been referred to as “Greening” the network and the protocols. For example, the EU-funded 6Green Project [7] has been conceived to rapidly evolve new paradigms with the energy saving/low-carbon-footprint principle as first objective. To achieve these goals, 5/6G will extend cloud-native technologies and Service Based Architecture to boost the global ecosystem flexibility, scalability and sustainability. It is necessary to identify where the reduction of energy consumption is most cost effective in term of improvements, as Internet can be divided into different segments with

different equipment [6] and thus different energy requirements, but also different protocols [8].

- The most promising in terms of improvement, of course, is at equipment level as it is essential to reduce the power consumption. This includes energy-saving modes, in which power is reduced in hardware that is not fully used.
- At protocol level, energy efficiency is rarely considered when are designed. For example, sometimes the need for redundant transmission or retransmission is reduced.
- At network level, energy savings are achieved by redirecting traffic to other devices that are already running, allowing others to be switched off or in power-saving mode. At the same time, energy can be saved by not waking up devices that are in sleep mode (this may require more energy than the operations actually performed) by always diverting the traffic to devices already in use.

As mentioned earlier, 5G has been planned from the outset as service-based, thus implementing the cloud, edge and NFV paradigms. Since a large number of small cells will be deployed with 5G, there will be an increase in RAN-related costs.

With C-RAN there will be the allocation of VNFs on demand, depending on the amount of data. However, although NFV brings many advantages in terms of scalability and flexibility, massive and uncontrolled deployment can lead to low energy efficiency. On the other hand, using VNFs together with specialised hardware solutions can save up to 20 per cent energy and reduce CapEx and OpEx [9].

On the core side, VNFs run on general-purpose hardware located in servers that have a Total Carbon Footprint (TCF) that is the sum of the Embodied Carbon Footprint (ECF) and the Operating Carbon Footprint. These are respectively the volume of greenhouse gases emitted for the purchase of the physical device and the emission due to the operation of the device itself. It is estimated that the 90% of the annual TCF of a single server is due to OCF. Studies [5] have seen that the use of a massive VNF deployment causes a critical increase in OCF of 106% over Business As Usual (BAU). It is therefore crucial to combine viable and efficient hardware and software solutions to reduce CO2 emissions and costs.

In addition, 6Green will extend the 5G SBA concept by transforming network slices into a dynamic environment capable of coordinating application and network requirements, reducing their energy consumption. In this way it is potentially reduced consumption to zero in all areas of the network slice that are not in use. In general, 6Green will rely heavily on Artificial Intelligence (AI) to support both 5G evolution and sustainability ambitions. Indeed, even simple AI will play a key role in energy and carbon footprint estimation.

III. SYSTEM UNDER TEST

A. System Setup

To set up the tests, the containers containing the 5G RAN and core were deployed on bare metal. In particular, a Next Unit of Computing (NUC) was used that is a small but powerful computer developed by Intel. The model used is the Intel NUC9VXQNX [10] that mounts an Intel Xeon E-

2286M 2.40 GHz processor with 8 cores and a maximum RAM of 64 GB. The OS installed on this machine is a Linux distro that is Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS.

The NUC was accessed and controlled remotely using a Virtual Private Network (VPN) via the toolbox MobaXterm [11] that provides Unix commands and remote network tools like SSH.

The tutorial made by Eurecom allowed to deploy the OpenAirInterface 5G core [12] with some small but crucial modifications. For the monitoring part five more containers were deployed for managing Prometheus [13], Grafana [14], cAdvisor [15], Scaphandre [16] and Raritan exporter [17].

The last exporter is necessary to monitor the UPFs that are explained below. Raritan is a company [18] that develops intelligent rack Power Distribution Units (PDUs) and gives the possibility to monitor and control the power consumption using a web interface. The NUC is powered by one of these intelligent plugs.

It is important to be on Intel bare metal since collecting metrics from Scaphandre running in a Virtual Machine become cumbersome due to an Intel module called Intel Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) [19].

The collection of the data was made using a Python program that takes the data from Prometheus retrieving the metrics and generates a .xlsx file for each number of parallel

Given that the eBPF-XDP UPF makes no use of the CPU, the only way to take comparable measurements between UPFs was to make the difference between the power supplied by the Raritan plug and all the processes that used the CPU but the UPF itself.

In this way there is also the power consumed by the non-monitorable components like disk, RAM, fans etc. but, at least, a comparison can be made because all those components that affects the measurements are present in both cases.

At the time the tests were made, no method using Prometheus queries existed to remove also the power consumption of the other components from the power supplied by the intelligent plug.

B. Vector Packet Processing Setup

This section is dedicated to the deployment of one of the UPF types offered by OAI, namely the Vector Packet Processing (VPP-UPF). VPP is a high speed software that delivers data plane functionalities like routing functions. Its main feature is that it works in a kernel-bypass mode and can run on commodity hardware (CPU) like the NUC. Bypassing the kernel means reducing drastically kernel calls increasing the processing.

The difference between VPP and a scalar packet processing is that the latter processes one packet at a time calling an interrupt and a set of functions. In general this is a simple but problematic way due mainly to the size of the L1 cache. Instead, Vector Packet Processing builds vectors of up to 256 packets and process them using a directed graph of node.

To set up the tests, a script was written to run the exchange of data between the container “oai-ext-dn” (that is the container representing an external network) and the RAN container through the UPF.

This code runs inside “oai-ext-dn” container and uses the Iperf3 command for the generation of traffic. Due to limitations of the Iperf3 command (particularly the limited bandwidth), the decision was to make the tests with 1, 10, 64 and 128 users (128 is the maximum available with Iperf3). A test with 100 users has been made later manually to have more comparison between the two UPFs. For each number of users, made as lists in the code, was also changed the number of bits per second.

30 Gb/s is the upper limit for Iperf3 running in container but, at a higher number of parallel users, it has more limitations in the generation of the bits and this was seen while running the tests. The tests, for each bandwidth, were conducted for one hour.

C. eXpress Data Path Setup

Originally was designed, as Berkeley Packet Filter (BPF), by McCanne and Jacobson [20]. Extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) [21] is a lightweight and fast virtual machine that resides into the Linux kernel. It offers a combination of performance, safety, flexibility and provides a programmable interface for developing custom code inside the Linux kernel at run-time without rebooting and without any change in the kernel code itself.

The eBPF is also attachable to any sub-process running in the kernel or, for example, exactly after the Network Card Interface (NIC). In fact, in this case is placed right after the NIC making it become the eXpress Data Path (XDP) that is an eBPF-based data path used to intercept packets as soon as they leave the NIC.

Before being executed, an eBPF program follows different step:

- Compilation step;
- Loading step;
- Verification step whose aim is to guarantee that the code does not harm the kernel;
- Just-In-Time (JIT) Compilation where the code is translated for the specific machine.

To deploy the core, the RAN emulator and the UPF was followed the Eurecom tutorial [22]. Unfortunately the code of the eBPF hides a problem that was not solved, that is a leak of memory due to malloc calls without freeing the resource. Due to this, the UPF container was able to stay healthy for about one hour, after which it exited with error code 1. For this motivation, the tests were run manually for about one hour, after which the UPF container was shot down and rebuilt again.

Also the Iperf3 command running inside the containers deployed with this tutorial had problems, in fact its maximum bandwidth was about 1 Gb/s and the maximum number of parallel users that let the command work properly was 100, so the data was acquired using those values as maximum.

Since all the processing is made right after the NIC, the CPU is completely unused for its functions by the UPF and this creates a problem for the monitoring part because Scaphandre uses internally the CPU load of a process to calculate power consumption. The method used to estimate

(a) Bandwidth

(b) Power Consumption

(c) CPU

(d) Memory

Figure 1. Results obtained for VPP-UPF with 1 user.

the power consumed by the eBPF-XDP was to collect the power metrics from Raritan, that is the power provided by the Raritan socket and subtract from it all the processes that used the CPU using the Scaphandre metric sum. The result is the combination of the eBPF power plus all the component of the NUC that are not measurable because they do not involve CPU (like LEDs, fans etc).

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. VPP

Figure 1 shows results obtained when testing the VPP-UPF with one user.

Figure 1a shows the different bandwidths generated for the test. On the x axis and y axis are shown, respectively, the time in the format h:mm and the values [Mb/s] in logarithmic scale. The lines present side values except the one representing 1 Mb/s. This is due to residual bandwidth of Iperf3 starting up and shutting down that is captured by cAdvisor. For each bandwidth, the value increases by a factor of 10 except for the last one representing the limit of the Iperf3 command, that is 30 Gb/s in the case of one user, indeed appear small fluctuations in the values.

Figure 1b represents the power consumption relative to one user. The x axis represents the time in the h:mm format while power consumption and standard deviation are represented, respectively, on the primary y axis and on the secondary y axis. The power consumption for one user is always stable around 33 [W] until 1 Gb/s, presents a small increase for 10 Gb/s and then has a big increase when reaches 30 Gb/s.

Figure 1c shows the percentage of CPU used by the Vector Packet Processing. The time, in the h:mm format, is represented on the x axis while the percentage on the y axis.

As expected, fluctuations appear for 1 Gb/s and become more visible at higher values.

Figure 1d represents the memory occupied by the container. Except very small fluctuations (300 KB) that are caused probably by internal processes of the Vector Packet Processing UPF, the memory occupied is always around 920 MB regardless of the throughput.

Figure 2 shows results obtained when testing the VPP-UPF with ten users.

Figure 2a shows the bandwidth generated by 10 users in parallel. Each value is the total throughput traversing the UPF. For example, the first line represents 10 users sending simultaneously 1 Mb/s, the second 10 Mb/s etc. The limit for the generation is 30 Gb/s, that is 3 Gb/s per user.

Figure 2b represents the power consumption for this test case. Until 4:40, the behaviour is quite stable, beside short peaks, around 33 W, whereas there is a sudden increase in the power at 4:54, that is the test with a total of 30 Gb/s.

Figure 2c shows the load, in percentage, over the CPU for 10 users in parallel. The graph presents well marked fluctuations at 3:45 (10 Gb/s) with a spike at the start of 30 Gb/s (4:57) that is probably due to internal processes of the UPF.

In Figure 2d is visible the occupation of memory in [MB].

These values never exceed the maximum of 920.7 MB, while the minimum is around 920.3 MB. The spikes are probably caused by internal processes of the UPF and gives a maximum difference of 350 KB.

Figure 3 shows results obtained when testing the VPP-UPF with one user.

Figure 3a shows the bandwidth generated having 100 parallel users. The visible side lines are again due to residual

Figure 2. Results obtained for VPP-UPF with 10 users.

bandwidth of Iperf3. In this case were captured in more detail by cAdvisor but did not affect the final results.

Unexpectedly, Figure 3b shows a decrease in the value. For example, the average power consumption having a total throughput of 10 Gb/s is lower than the previous case. This test was run several time to have sure values.

Figure 3c shows that the usage of the CPU is quite stable around the same values of the previous cases, while Figure 3d presents smaller values in the memory usage. In particular, the values are around 908.85 MB.

B. XDP

As stated before, since results for the eBPF-XDP collected for each bandwidth separately, only the highest one (e.g., 1 Gbit/s) for one user is shown for sake of brevity. The remaining values will be presented in the summary.

Figure 4a shows the bandwidth with 1 user generating 1 Gb/s, that is the limit for the Iperf3 command in the cases with eBPF. The slight instability is due to this upper limit and does not affect the final results. On the x axis, the time is represented in the format h:mm because the test lasted for more than an hour.

Figure 4b shows the power consumption on the y axis, while the time is represented on the x axis in the format h:mm. Due to an error in the collection of the metrics, the test is considered valid starting from 0:03 to 1:02.

Figure 4c shows, on the y axis, the percentage of CPU utilized by the eBPF-XDP while, on the x axis, the time in format mm:ss. As stated before, this kind of UPF does not load the CPU, in fact the values are around 0.01%.

The utilized memory, as seen from Figure 4d, never exceed 1 MB.

C. Summary

Figure 5 and Figure 6 shows all the average powers gathered from the tests. On the x axis are visible the number of parallel users, while on the y axis the values in [W].

The different colors represent the bandwidths generated per user. From Figure 5 is visible that the power, for the Vector Packet Processing, never goes below 30 W even for very low traffic. For the first three cases (1, 10 and 64 users) the values are quite stable except for high traffic per user where a sudden increase brings the power consumption around 60 W. The last cases (100 and 128 users) have less data due to the maximum limit of Iperf3 generation.

Figure 6 shows the results for the Extended Berkeley Packet Filter - eXpress Data Path. For low traffic, the power is quite stable around 25 W while, increasing the value in bit transmission, never exceeds 35 W.

The comparison between the two User Plane Functions is visible in Figure 7. On the x axis are represented the common number of parallel users, while on the y axis are shown the values gathered as the difference between the average power of the VPP and the eBPF-XDP. In particular, positive values mean lower power consumption of the eBPF-XDP, while negative values lower power consumption of the VPP. As seen, the eBPF-XDP has, in general, better performances at low traffic while the VPP behaves better at higher traffic rate. In the last case is visible less data due to the maximum limit of Iperf3 generation.

(a) Bandwidth

(b) Power Consumption

(c) CPU

(d) Memory

Figure 3. Results obtained for VPP-UPF with 100 users.

(a) Bandwidth

(b) Power Consumption

(c) CPU

(d) Memory

Figure 4. Results obtained for xDP-UPF with 1 user at 1Gbit/s.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper was made a comparison between two approaches in developing the 5G User Plane Function. In fact 5G is the present and the future of the worldwide telecommunication systems and has to deal with the climate changes caused by human activities, in particular due to carbon dioxide emissions.

The core was deployed using a 3GPP implementation of a software developed by OpenAirInterface and Docker containers.

Results have shown a better performance of the Extended Berkeley Packet Filtering - eXpress Data Path. Since it does not require the use of CPU, it is impossible, until today, to have precise measurements using the Prometheus exporter called Scaphandre, so estimations were made computing the difference between the power supplied by the Raritan plug and the processes that were measurable, thus including in the values also the power consumed by disk, fans, RAM etc. In any case, using the same method to acquire the data for both UPFs, it was possible to make a comparison between the two.

Regarding the CPU usage in the VPP test case, the percentage never goes beyond 9%. In the cases where this value is higher for a lower number of parallel users, it is probably due to some errors in the estimations of the cAdvisor exporter, since the power consumption is greater.

Further works can also take into account another important parameter that is the latency between the interfaces of the UPFs and then generate an algorithm to dynamically change the type of UPF based on the required latency and on the power.

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Figure 5. Power comparison for VPP.

Figure 6. Power comparison for eBPF.

Figure 7. Comparison of the two UPFs.

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